

INVESTIGATION OF THE ANTI-INFLAMMATORY AND ANALGESIC ACTIVITY OF A POLYSACCHARIDE FROM *BRASSICA RAPA* SEEDS

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Abstract. At present, when the fact of more complete use of local plant resources is of particular importance, interest in plant polysaccharides isolated from vegetable crops growing in Uzbekistan with lower toxicity is increasing. Previously, we studied the immunomodulatory, antidiabetic, hypoglycemic, hepatoprotective activity of polysaccharide from *Brassica rapa* seeds as a promising source of medicines and preventive agents. After a number of studies conducted in the Laboratory of Pharmacology and biologically active additives (BAA) Screening to study the biological activity of this polysaccharide isolated in the Laboratory of Protein and Peptide Chemistry, we consider it as a biologically active substance that can be used to produce a biologically active food additive. The polysaccharide isolated from the seeds of the local vegetable crop *Brassica rapa* can be used as a medicinal product or a biologically active food additive. Further, it is of absolute interest to study the mechanism of anti-inflammatory and analgesic action of *Brassica rapa* polysaccharides.

Keywords: *Brassica rapa*, arthritis, cancer, asthma, atherosclerosis and autoimmune diseases, monocytes, macrophages.

The aim of this study is to evaluate the potential of *Brassica rapa* polysaccharide for anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity using a model of paw edema caused by carrageenan in rats and hot plate in mice.

Inflammation is part of the complex biological response of body tissues to harmful stimuli, including pathogens, damaged cells, or irritating factors. However, excessive inflammatory reactions characterized by dilation of blood vessels, production of pro-inflammatory molecules, release of cytokines and an increase in the number of white blood cells can be harmful. Inflammation is the main protective reaction of the primary immune system against damage and is characterized by both acute and chronic inflammation [1,2]. Acute inflammation leads to the formation of edema, infiltration by leukocytes and macrophages in the damaged muscle [3]. Whereas in chronic inflammation, prolonged infiltration of these components of the immune system leads to more serious conditions such as arthritis, cancer, asthma, atherosclerosis and autoimmune diseases [4]. Most health problems appear only when the inflammation persists for a long time and is irreversible. Inflammation triggers the production of cytokines, including immunosuppressive interleukins (IL-) 4 and IL-10, or pro-carcinogenic IL-6 and TNF- α [5].

Anti-inflammatory drugs obtained from natural sources and used in traditional medicine attract the attention of healthcare professionals and the pharmaceutical industry due to their effectiveness and fewer side effects [1,2,4]. Plant polysaccharides have pronounced anti-inflammatory, wound healing, antioxidant and anti-radiation effects, stimulate hematopoiesis processes, activate the functions of the immune system when injected into the body as healthy animals, as well as animals with various types of pathology [6, 7]. Entering the body through the

mouth, intramuscularly or intravenously, polysaccharides primarily affect the system of macrophages and monocytes, enhancing their physiological functions. This leads to: 1) activate the synthesis of signaling molecules that activate lymphocytes, leukocytes, and the complement system; 2) stimulate phagocytosis; 3) increase the number of monocytes and macrophages in the blood of animals by 2-3 times. *Brassica rapa*, commonly known as turnip, is an edible root vegetable, eaten as a vegetable, which belongs to the *Brassicaceae* family [8, 9, 10]. *Brassica rapa* is a rich source of biologically active compounds, including isothiocyanates, glucosinolates, anthocyanins, carotenoids, flavonoids, sulforaphane, organic acids and phenolic compounds [11, 12]. The plant was used not only for nutrition, but also as a traditional remedy against a number of diseases, including inflammation [2]. It has been reported that ethanol turnip extract exhibits an antiarthritic effect against inflammation caused by Freund's adjuvant and has an incredible anti-inflammatory effect and analgesic potential [2].

Material and methods. The material was a polysaccharide from *Brassica rapa* seeds at a dose of 20 mg/kg and the comparison drug Indomethacin (NSAID) Sofarma 25 mg/kg (tablets coated with an intestinal membrane, GTIN 03800010643153. Series No. 32F23. Valid until 06/28. CH: NT1GXR8X4VSQT). The anti-inflammatory potential *in vivo* was assessed by induced carrageenan edema of the rat paw, and the analgesic potential was investigated using a hot plate test. The results showed that the polysaccharide reduced paw edema, it was noted that the analgesic effect was also more pronounced compared to the drug Indomethacin. It can be concluded that the polysaccharide demonstrates a stronger suppression of inflammation, having a strong anti-inflammatory and analgesic effect. To determine the anti-inflammatory and analgesic potential *in vivo*, before starting experimental work, the animals were kept indoors for 10 days in quarantine for acclimatization. All standard requirements were met in the animal room, such as ambient temperature ($25\pm 3^{\circ}\text{C}$), a 12-hour "dark/light" cycle and a humidity range (30-70%), which were necessary for the survival of rats. The rats were fed regular food and given unlimited amounts of water. After acclimatization, the rats were randomly assigned six rats per group/cell. A model of acute inflammation, carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats. To assess the anti-inflammatory potential of *Brassica rapa* seed polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg and the comparison drug Indomethacin Sopharma at a dose of 25 mg/kg, the animals were divided into three groups, 6 rats each: the normal control group (CG) (received only food, drink and regular saline solution orally), group 2 I received polysaccharide (20 mg/kg) and food, drink, positive control group 3 (CG) (I received indomethacin (25 mg/kg)) and food, drink. To study acute inflammation, a carrageenan-induced paw edema model was performed using the described method [13]. A tampon containing 0.05 ml of 1% sodium salt of carrageenan was inserted into the right hind leg of each rat under plantar aponeurosis. The experimental group of rats was orally administered the studied drugs 1 hour before carrageenan injection. At the same time, the control group was given 5 ml/kg of saline solution. The experimental group received a polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg, whereas the positive control group was administered indomethacin at a dose of 25 mg/kg, the percentage of inhibition was calculated by taking the values in the control group for 0% inhibition. An electronic vernier caliper (Insize, model 7140, Digital Caliper, 0-150mm/0-6, China) was used to measure the paw diameter (PV₀) before and after 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 hours after carrageenan injection (PV_t). Suppression of edema in the treated groups compared to the control group. The control group was calculated using the following equation: % Inhibition of inflammation = $(\text{PV}_t - \text{PV}_0)_{\text{control}} - (\text{PV}_t - \text{PV}_0)_{\text{treated}} / (\text{PV}_t - \text{PV}_0)_{\text{control}} \times 100$, where PV_t represents the diameter of inflammation

in a rat after carrageenan, and PV₀ represents the diameter of inflammation in a rat treated before carrageenan.

Analgesic activity. To assess the analgesic activity of the polysaccharide, the animals were divided into the following groups of 6 rats each: 1-normal control group (CG) (received only standard food and ordinary saline solution orally), 2-group (received polysaccharide (20 mg/kg) together with food and ordinary saline solution orally), 3-positive control group (CG) (received indomethacin (25 mg/kg) with food and regular saline solution orally). The analgesic potential was assessed using the hot plate method described by Fan et al. [14] with minor changes. The experimental group was given polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg for 7 days, while the positive control group was treated with indomethacin at a dose of 25 mg/kg. On day 7, analgesic activity was performed in all rats of the experimental group after 1 hour of administration of extracts and indomethacin. Each rat from all groups was placed on a hot plate in a glass cup at a temperature of 55 ± 0.5 °C. The rat's reaction time to pain stimuli and distress behavior, including jumping and licking paws, was monitored. The latency period or duration of the pain reaction was recorded by a stopwatch in seconds. Before administration of the dose, the first value was observed at time 0, while the remaining values were observed at intervals of 30, 60, 90 and 120 minutes (min) after receiving the polysaccharide and taking the drug. The shutdown time to prevent any injury was fixed at 12 seconds. This was seen as controlling the reaction time to pain. The maximum possible analgesia (MPA) was determined by the following formula: $MPA (\%) = \frac{\text{Reaction time to treatment} - \text{The reaction time to saline solution}}{12 (\text{the reaction time to saline solution})} \times 100$. According to statistical analysis, the differences between the indicators of the compared groups of animals were considered statistically significant if the probability value (p) was < 0.05 .

The results of the research. The effect of *B. rapa* polysaccharide and indomethacin on carrageenan-induced paw edema is shown in Table 1. *B. rapa* polysaccharide significantly reduced carrageenan-induced inflammation by reducing the paw diameter of rats (Fig. 1). In this study, the maximum decrease in paw diameter was observed 3 hours after carrageenan injection (Fig. 1). During the fourth and after the fifth hour of observation (h), rats treated with *B. rapa* polysaccharide showed more significant inhibition compared to normal control. At that time, indomethacin has an inhibitory effect of 27.52 and 27.63%.

Fig. 1. Representative images of rat paws after carrageenan injection: (a) normal control group; (b) polysaccharide group *B. rapa*; (c) positive control group (indomethacin) 3 hours after carrageenan administration

The anti-inflammatory effect of *B. rapa* polysaccharide. It consists in the fact that the introduction of plant polysaccharides to animals with inflammation slows down the growth of tissue edema, shortens the time for normalization of the cellular composition of blood and tissues,

shortens the duration of treatment. The anti-inflammatory effect of plant polysaccharides is realized by changing the permeability of the vascular wall in the focus of inflammation, activating phagocytosis, enzyme activity of phagocytes and increasing their number. Polysaccharides activate synthesis processes, which accelerates the restoration of tissue structure in the focus of inflammation. Polysaccharides enhance the antioxidant activity of cells and tissues by activating enzyme systems [6, 7].

Table 1

Effect of B. rapa polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg and indomethacin at a dose of 25 mg/kg on % suppression of inflammation in carrageenan-induced paw edema in rats

Group	Inhibition of inflammation, % h - hour				
	1 h	2 h	3 h	4 h	5 h
Polysaccharide <i>Brp</i>	58.2±7.79	48.27±5.05	41.17±7.01	47.92±5.27 p=0.0498	52.35±3.00 p=0.0126
Indomethacin	40.49±5.89	39.83±3.55	29.50±3.06	27.52±7.31	27.63±7.38

The analysis of scientific literature revealed the high anti-inflammatory activity of sulfated plant pectins, carrageenan, laminaride, which reduce edema and cause active proliferation of synovial and collagen tissue cells [16, 17]. Currently, one of the important areas of research is the modulation of the immune system. In the treatment of inflammatory and allergic diseases, it is necessary to suppress the immune system, while stimulation of the immune system is highly desirable for the treatment of HIV, immunodeficiency and infectious diseases. Previously, we studied the immunomodulatory effect of the sum of polysaccharides from *B. rapa* seeds on animal models of delayed-type hypersensitivity (HRT) - a model of cell-mediated response, which is clearly determined in vivo. It has been proven that the polysaccharides of the seeds of *B. rapa* have immunomodulatory properties [18]. However, further pharmacological and phytochemical studies are needed to identify the components of *B. rapa* and accurately assess their immunomodulatory activity and mechanisms.

Analgesic activity. Table 2 shows the effect of *B. rapa* polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg and indomethacin at a dose of 25 mg/kg on analgesic activity. The hot plate method was used to evaluate thermal stimulation of the skin and measure the time it takes for a rat to jump or lick to analyze its potential effects. The administration of *B. rapa* polysaccharide (20 mg/kg) caused an important stimulating effect in the rat by increasing the latency time. 90 minutes after administration of the polysaccharide dose (20 mg/kg), the maximum latency of thermal stimulation was achieved compared with the control group. Overall, the polysaccharide group demonstrated strong analgesic potential after 90 minutes, and the substance was found to be effective in relieving pain. These results are confirmed by previous results when treatment with *B. rapa* polysaccharide for diabetes mellitus in rats provided significant dose-dependent pain relief [19].

Along with the anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects of the studied drugs, the effect on the immune system of NSAID indomethacin at a dose of 25 mg/kg for rats, taken in this experiment as a positive control for comparing the anti-inflammatory activity of *Brassica rapa* polysaccharide should be noted. The effect of indomethacin is revealed in the inhibition of lymphocyte transformation caused by various antigens, thereby NSAIDs act as an immunosuppressant. The immunosuppressive effect is also determined by: a decrease in capillary permeability, which makes it difficult for immunocompetent cells to contact the antigen, antibodies with the substrate;

stabilization of lysosomal membranes in macrophages, which limits the cleavage of poorly soluble antigens necessary for the development of the next stages of the immune reaction [20].

Table 2

The effect of B. rapa polysaccharide and indomethacin on the analgesic activity of animals (mice)

Group	Reaction time, min.				
	The original time	30	60	90	120
Control	3.49±0.12	3.50±0.16	3.52±0.20	3.50±0.21	3.56±0.24
Polysaccharide <i>Brp</i>	3.59±0.25	6.20±0.28 p=0.000015	6.45±0.30 p=0.00002	6.91±0.34 p=0.000013	6.26±0.28 p=0.000045
Indomethacin	3.50±0.17	6.38±0.28 p=0.000009	6.92±0.32 p=0.000008	6.84±0.32 p=0.000011	5.75±0.30 p=0.00029

p ≤ 0.05 relative to the control.

Conclusions. It can be concluded that the polysaccharide from *B. rapa* seeds showed greater anti-inflammatory potential than the positive control, since a reduced incidence of inflammation was observed in the group of animals receiving polysaccharide from *Brassica rapa* seeds. The results of analgesic activity also showed that rats treated with polysaccharide experienced less pain compared to the group of animals of positive control. Theoretically, the activity of the polysaccharide is accompanied by suppression of TNF- α , IL-6 and CRP levels, which reduces the development of inflammation and pain. Polysaccharide at a dose of 20 mg/kg is the best anti-inflammatory extract with the greatest potential for suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines along with analgesic activity.

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